
**A Study of Growth of Census Towns and Emerging Urban Centers in
Karad Taluka, Satara District (Maharashtra)**

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Abstract:

Karad Taluka is an important place in Satara district. It has important political, educational and agricultural background. Hence, it has emerged some census towns and urban centers. Karad is an notable and most important urban center in Satara District. The statutory Urban local bodies are municipalities and for rural it has Panchayat samiti.

The unit of classification in this regard is 'town' for urban areas and 'village' for rural areas. The urban area comprises two types of towns viz: Statutory towns and Census towns. In the Census of India 2011, the definition of urban area adopted is as follows: (a) Statutory Towns: All places with a municipality, corporation, cantonment board or notified town area committee, etc. are known as Statutory Towns. (b) Census Towns: The following three criteria simultaneously are treated as Census Town. A census town is defined as one where i) the population is at least 5,000 people, ii) the population density is 400 people per square kilometer, iii) at least 75% of the working-age male population is employed in non-agricultural activities.

Cities or areas that are undergoing rapid expansion, development, and transformation are referred to as "Emerging Urban Centers" because of their notable advancements in infrastructure, social improvement, and the economy.

Key words: Census Towns and Emerging Urban Centers

Introduction:

Karad is an important political hub in Satara district. Former Chief Minister of Maharashtra Late Yashwantrao Chavan Saheb and Karad Nagarparishad President P. D. Patil Saheb have both worked tirelessly to development Karad Taluka. Hence, Karad Taluka has various educational societies, research center, each and every health facility, and transport facilities is available in Karad Taluka.

Objectives:

To study the *Census Towns and Emerging Urban Centers* in Karad Taluka

Methodology:

The researcher has been given a field visit for the study. So the primary information is received through field work. Secondary data was collected from Satara District Gazette. After collecting the secondary data, the researcher has used different statistical methods for tabulation and attempted to show the obtained information through a map and diagrams.

Study Region:

Karad Taluka is selected for present investigation. It extends from 17⁰16' north to 17⁰33' north latitude and 73⁰52' east to 74⁰16' east longitude. Karad Taluka comprises in area of 405.8 sq. Km. Its maximum temperature is up to 42⁰c and

minimum 15⁰c Annual rain fall is 700 mm and Relative humidity is 85 per cent in the rainy season. Its climate is monsoonal type

and it is favorable and healthy for human living and other living things.

Data Analysis:

Growth of Census Towns in Karad Taluka (1961- 2021)

A census town is defined as one where i) the population is at least 5,000 people, ii) the population density is 400 people per square kilometer, iii) at least 75% of the working-age male population is employed in non-agricultural activities.

Statutory towns and metropolitan regions differ from census towns in that they do not have a municipal administration or board. Despite having urban characteristics, they are not officially designated as urban areas. Census towns have gained significance in the Indian context due to the swift establishment of new urban centers and the swift increase in urbanization.

Table 1.1: Growth of Urban Centers in Karad Taluka (1961-2021)

Years	No .of Urban Centers (Census Towns)	Percent
1961	01	5.88
1971	02	11.76
1981	01	5.88
1991	01	5.88
2001	02	11.76
2011	05	29.41
2021	05	29.41
Total	17	100

Source: District Census Handbook, Satara (1961 to 2011)

In the year 1961 to 1991 it means forty years of the period in Karad Taluka having only one census town in 1961 and two urban centers in 1971. In this year Karad (M CI) and Vanavadi (Sadashivgad) was urban centers (11.76%). In 1981 and 1991 there was one urban center (5.88%) respectively viz. Karad (M CI). In 2001 the number is increased and it goes to two urban centers (11.76%) viz. Karad (M CI) and Vanavadi (Sadashivgad) (CT). After the ten years in 2011, the number of urban centers are increased and it goes to five (29.41%). The name of increased urban centers is Karad (M CI), Malkapur (NP), Saidapur (CT), Karad (Rural) and Hajarmachi (CT). In 2021, its five towns in Karad Taluka and percent of it was 29.41. By the Census of India 2021 declared the same urban centers for the census year 2021.

Emerging Urban Centers in Karad Taluka (2001-2011):

Rapid development and growth in terms of population, infrastructure, and economic activity are common in emerging metropolitan centers. Cities or areas that are undergoing rapid expansion, development, and transformation are referred to as "Emerging Urban Centers" because of their notable advancements in infrastructure, social improvement, and the economy. These regions are frequently distinguished by quick urbanization, a rise in economic activity, and the construction of contemporary infrastructure. The designation "emerging" implies that these centers are now gaining prominence on a national or international level.

Table 1.2: Emerging Urban Centers in Karad Taluka (2001-2011)

Name of Urban Regions	Area in sq. km	2001			2011		
		No. of Households	Total Population	Density of Population	No. of Households	Total Population	Density of Population
Shere	9.26	1024	5205	562	1152	5369	580
Rethare(Bk.)	14.88	2307	11853	797	2397	12004	807
Wing	10.53	1276	6317	600	1460	6604	627
Umbraj	5.77	2872	14431	2501	3714	16854	2921
Saidapur	5.93	2065	10175	1716	3135	9317	2389
Hajarmachi	3.89	1750	8330	2141	2027	13913	2358
Masur	12.15	1564	7966	656	1883	8933	735
Warunji	6.16	1121	5452	885	1355	6136	996
Pal	16.29	1263	6428	395	1395	6619	406
Munde	6.54	818	4344	664	1002	5051	772
Koparde Haveli	9.02	1129	6298	698	1244	6207	688
Karve	9.15	1523	7858	859	1574	7451	814
Goleshwar	6.27	1140	5396	861	1430	6864	1095
Charegaon	9.08	1185	9894	649	1117	5398	594
Kale	13.56	1919	9493	700	1839	8741	645
Vadgaon Haveli	13.96	1274	6460	463	1395	6825	489

Source: District Census Handbook, Satara (2011)

Above table 1.2 shows the Population density of Karad Taluka during 2001 to 2011 census. Under the category of emerging urban centers in Karad Taluka, there are a total 16 emerging urban centers. The population density of the Shere sub-urban center was 562 persons per sq.km in 2001 and 580 persons per sq.km in 2011. Likewise, no. of households were 1024 and 1152 respectively. The population density of the Rethare (Bk.) sub-urban center was 797 persons per sq.km in 2001 and 807 persons per sq.km in 2011.

Alike, no. of households was 2307 and 2397 respectively. The population density of the Wing sub-urban center was 600 persons per sq.km in 2001 and 627 persons per sq.km. in 2011. Likewise, no. of households were 1276 and 1460 respectively. The population density of the Umbraj sub-urban center was 2,921 persons per sq.km in 2011 compared to 2,501 persons per sq. km in 2001. In it has 2872 and 3714 no. of households in both year respectively. The population density of the Saidapur was 1716 and 2389 in 2001 and 2011 respectively. Also, in Hajarmachi the population density of it was 2141 and 2358 in 2001 and 2011 respectively.

Masur sub-urban center was 656 persons per sq.km in 2001 and 735 persons per sq.km in 2011 respectively. As well as, 1564 and 1883 no. of households respectively. The population density of the Warunji sub-urban center was 885 persons per sq.km in 2001 and 996 persons per sq. km in 2011. It holds 1121 and 1355 no. of households. Pal is the religious place in Karad Taluka. It has 395 and 406 persons per sq.km in 2001 and 2011 respectively. As well as, it has 1263 and 1395 no. of households in both year respectively. In Munde sub-urban center has 664 and 772 persons per sq.km respectively and it has 818 and 1002 no. of households in both year.

In Koparde Haveli sub urban center was 698 persons and 688 persons per sq.km in both year. Likewise, no. of households was 1129 and 1244 in both year. In the year 2001, in Karve was 859 persons and 814 persons per sq.km in 2011. It was 1523 and 1574 households population in both year. In Goleshwar sub-urban center, in the year 2001, was 861 persons per sq.km and in 2011, it had 1095 persons per sq.km and it holds 1140 and 1430 households in both year. In the year 2001, in Charegaon was 649 persons per sq.km and 594 persons per sq.km in both year. Likewise, it had 1185 and 1117 no. of households in both year. There was slightly decrease in no. of households and population density. In Kale sub-urban center was 700 and 645 persons per sq.km in both year. Also, in the year 2001, no. of households were 1919 and 1839 in the year 2011. The population density of the Vadgaon Haveli sub-urban center was 463 in 2001 and 489 in 2011. As well as, there was 1274 and 1395 no. of households in both year.

Karad Taluka has an average 562 persons per sq.km. Karad Taluka is the most thickly populated Taluka in the Satara district. In this Taluka, Karad (MCI) has highest density of population. It has 21381 population per sq.km. Malkapur is the second largest density of population. It has 3726 population per sq.km. After that Umbraj has 2921 density of population, Saidapur has 2389 density of population, Hajarmachi has 2358 density of population, Karad (Rural) has 1212 density of population and Goleshwar has 1095 density of population per sq.km. These population densities is comparatively higher than Satara district and Maharashtra state.

Conclusion:

After the 1961 to 2021 years, the number of urban centers are increased and it goes to five (29.41%). The name of increased urban centers is Karad (M CI), Malkapur (NP), Saidapur (CT), Karad (Rural) and Hajarmachi (CT).

As per the Population density of Karad Taluka during 2001 to 2011 census, emerging urban centers in Karad Taluka, there are a total 16 emerging urban centers.

Karad Taluka has an average 562 persons per sq.km. Karad Taluka is the most thickly populated Taluka in the Satara district. In this Taluka, Karad (MCI) has highest density of population. It has 21,381 population per sq.km. Malkapur is the second largest density of population. It has 3,726 population per sq.km. After that Umbraj has 2,921 density of population, Saidapur has 2,389 density of population, Hajarmachi has 2,358 density of population, Karad (Rural) has 1,212 density of population and Goleshwar has 1,095 density of population per sq.km. These population densities is comparatively higher than Satara district and Maharashtra state.

During the 1961 to 2011 there was ups and downs in level of Urbanization of Karad Taluka. In 2011 and 2021, Urbanisation became reached up to high level. Because, in study area seen that there has increased in growth of population, educational facilities, health care facilities, amusement facilities, per capita income, and proportion of main workers.

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